

Quantum Flux and Force in a Rotating Frame

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In a previous note (1), the Schrodinger time-independent equation is divided by the wavefunction and then a spatial derivative taken. This leads to an equation with force $= -d/dx V(x)$ present. Then, $d/dx (d/dx W / W)$ is written microscopically as $(\text{Sum over } p \quad p^3 f(p) \exp(ipx)) / W - (d/dx d/dx W)/W (d/dx W)/W$. Here $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. Thus, force is related to a microscopic average kinetic energy flux minus an average kinetic energy times an average flux. In this note, we try to examine the same situation in a rotating frame and examine force in this case and also try to consider microscopic features of $V(r)$.

Rotating Frames

In classical physics, $d/dt = d/dt' + \omega \times r$ links time derivatives in the lab frame d/dt to time derivatives d/dt' in the rotating frame. ω is the angular momentum vector. Thus, if one writes Newton's second law in a rotating frame, one obtains $d/dt' d/dt'$ together with pseudo-potential terms, one of them depending on velocity. In (1), it is suggested that the rotating frame with its velocity dependent potential may be treated in the same manner as a quantum problem utilizing the Lorentz force $q\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$. In the end, the following Hamiltonian is written in the rotating frame:

$$(1/2m)(-i\hbar d/dx - \omega \times r)^2 W(r) - 1/(2m) (\omega \times r)^2 W(r) + V(r) W(r) = E W(r) \quad ((1))$$

To try to understand ((1)), consider a particle at rest in the lab frame. For a person in a rotating frame, such a particle moves in a circle with angular velocity ω . This is p' for this person. In addition, there must be a potential proportional to $(\omega \times r)^2$, otherwise such motion could not occur. The person in the lab frame knows that p' is not the correct momentum, rather $p = p' + \omega \times r$ should be used so $p' = -i\hbar d/dx - \omega \times r$, but the $(\omega \times r)^2$ potential should be kept because it does not involve time derivatives. Such an argument, it seems leads to ((1)) without considering arguments related to Lorentz force or velocity dependent potentials.

Another paper (2), considers a rotating frame as being obtainable via a Lorentz boost, and then takes the nonrelativistic limit of this boost to obtain the Schrodinger equation in a rotating frame. Again, ((1)) is obtained.

One may rewrite ((1)) using:

$$(p' + \omega \times r)^2 = (-i\hbar d_j + e_{jlm} \omega_l r_m) (-i\hbar d_j + e_{jpq} \omega_p r_q) \quad \text{where } e_{jlm} \text{ is the Levi-Civita symbol.}$$

((1)) then becomes:

$$(-\hbar^2 d_j d_j / 2m - 1/m \omega L_z) W(r) = (E - V(r)) W(r) \quad ((2))$$

In ((2)), ωL_z where $L_z = -i\hbar x d/dy + i\hbar y d/dx$ has the appearance of a constraint term. By going into a rotating frame, it seems one constrains part of the motion to be rotational. L_z is the generator of rotations, but in ((2)) $-1/m \omega L_z$ has units of energy. In this note, we wish to examine how microscopic force is created in a rotating frame.

If one divides ((2)) by the wavefunction $W(r)$ and then takes a spatial derivative, say d/dy , one may obtain terms, each equivalent to a force. The objective in doing this is to try to obtain a microscopic sense of force.

In previous notes, it has been argued that quantum bound states involve unusual two channel conditional probability. The two channels are linked in a periodic manner i.e. $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$. In other words, we argue there is physical meaning to the Fourier series basis function. To calculate an average, say $p^*p/2m$ one writes: $(\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^*p/2m f(p) \exp(ipx))$. Thus, there is 'interference' because one is considering an overall average of a two channel periodic system. We argue this is a microscopic picture of quantum mechanics, although it should be pointed out a particle can be in only one state $\exp(ipx)$ at any instant. When going from a lab frame to a rotating one $p=p' + wxr$, but wxr is perpendicular to r and so does not contribute to the dot product of p and r (vectors).

Thus, taking d/dy of ((2)) after dividing by W first yields:

$$(-d/dy d_j d_j W/2mW) - (1/2m) (-d/dy d/dy W / W) (d/dy W / W) - 1/m w (d/dy L_z W)/W + 1/m w (L_z W / W) (d/dy W/W) = -d/dy V(r) \quad ((3))$$

Note: $d/dy L_z W = (d/dy L_z) W + L_z d/dy W$.

One may notice a certain pattern arising in ((3)). The first two terms are the difference of an averaged microscopic kinetic energy flux: $\text{Average}(p_y p_j p_j) - \text{Average}(p^*p) \text{Average}(p_y)$. This difference has the effect of a force. For the angular momentum term, one sees a similar thing. $(wL_z W)/W$ has the units of energy, so if it differs from point to point, a type of energy (related to rotation) is differing, suggesting the presence of a force. Again, one has a microscopic averaged flux $\text{Average}(p_x + y p_x^* p_y - x p_y^* p_y) - \text{Average}(p_y) \text{Average}(x p_y - y p_x)$. It has been argued in various notes that $\text{Average}(p_y)$ is a physical flux in the system. Thus, force seems to be related to a difference of a microscopic average of a certain p_x, p_y, x, y terms and an average energy type term multiplied by an average flux. This holds both for the kinetic energy and the rotational $wL_z W/W$ term. It should be noted that one is dealing with averages, even though a particle can be in only one state at a time. Thus, the whole idea of force seems to be an average one, furthermore, it is related to differences in different averages.

In ((3)), the term $-d/dy V(r)$ appears. One may ask whether it may also be expressed in microscopic terms. Consider:

$$-d/dy (V(r)W(r)/W) = V(r) (d/dy W/W) - ((d/dy V) W + V d/dy W)/W \quad ((4))$$

Writing V and W as Fourier series in the second term yields:

$$V(r) (d/dy W/W) - (\text{Sum over } p_1, p_2 \text{ } p_1(\text{vector}) V(p_1) f(p_2) \exp(i p_1 + p_2) + \text{Sum over } p_1, p_2 \text{ } p_2(\text{vector}) V(p_1) f(p_2) \exp(i p_1 + p_2)) / W \quad ((5))$$

Thus, one has an average of momentum terms from the Fourier transforms minus $V(r)$ times the flux. This again follows the pattern.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems that force in quantum mechanics is related to the difference in a certain microscopic average (kinetic energy flux for example) minus the product of a related average energy (e.g. kinetic energy) term times an average flux. If no force is present and there is only kinetic energy, the microscopic average of p^3 equals the average of p^2 times the average of p . Given that:

Average(p^3) is proportional to $(d/dx)^3 W / W$ and Average(p^2)Average(p) is proportional to $(d/dx d/dx W)(d/dx W) / (W^2)$, kinetic energy for such a case is constant and so the third and first derivative of W are proportional. With kinetic energy = $(-1/2m) d/dx d/dx W / W$ as a constant, this seems to imply periodicity in W if the first and third derivatives divided by W are not constant.

Force seems to be more than an average quantity, but a difference of averages. This seems to hold not only for a kinetic energy term or a $V(r)$ terms, but also for energy terms related to constrained motion, such as rotational motion.

References

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